

Mechanically-Interlocked Nitrogenated Nanographenes

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ABSTRACT: Herein, we report the synthesis of mechanically-interlocked nitrogenated nanographenes. These systems have been obtained by clipping different tetralactam macrocycles around a 1.9 nm dumbbell-shaped nitrogenated nanographene. Thermal, optoelectronic and electrochemical characterization of the different mechanically-interlocked nanographenes evidence enhanced thermal and photochemical stability, and also, absorption and emission properties that vary with the structure of the macrocycle.

Introduction

Rotaxane formation provides a unique strategy to improve the performance of molecules, polymers and materials without altering their covalent structure. The encapsulation of π -conjugated one-dimensional (1D) materials – such as polyenes,¹ polyynes,² cumulenes,³ polythiophenes (PTs),⁴ poly-*p*-phenylenes (PPPs),⁵ poly-*p*-phenylethynylenes (PPEs),⁶ conjugated copolymers,⁷ and single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs)⁸ (Figure 1) – with different macrocycles has shown to increase the chemical,³ thermal^{2e,3} and photochemical^{1a,1c} stability; modulate optoelectronic,^{6,9} redox,^{1b,8c} and mechanical¹⁰ properties; avoid aggregation that can interfere with their optoelectronic properties;^{5,11} insulate electronic/excitonic transport along the conjugated thread⁶ or even to introduce catalytic or mechanical properties.^{8d,10}

Nanographenes are polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) that extend over 1 nm.¹² Nanographenes show highly tunable optoelectronic, redox, and charge and exciton transporting properties that vary with the number of fused aromatic rings and their arrangement, and also, with the number and position of embedded heteroatoms in the aromatic framework. Nanographenes that extend in 1D, such as ribbon-shaped nanographenes and graphene nanoribbons,¹³ are attracting a lot of attention because of their unique edge-, width- and length dependent electronic, optical and mechanical properties and their potential to develop new materials for electronics,¹⁴ photonics,¹⁵ and energy conversion,¹⁶ among others. Even if, several PAHs are known to form supramolecular complexes with macrocycles¹⁷ and cages,¹⁷ and have been used as templates and recognition motifs in rotaxanes,¹⁸ mechanically-interlocked nanographenes remain unexplored and their synthesis will open up new opportunities to modify non-covalently the properties of nanographenes and also to introduce new ones.

Herein, we report the synthesis of mechanically-interlocked nitrogenated nanographenes (Figure 1 and Scheme 1). These systems have been obtained by clipping different tetralactam macrocycles around a 1.9 nm dumbbell-shaped nanographene (tetrabenzotetraazaheptacene **1**), in which the sp^2 nitrogen atoms embedded in the nanographene framework serve as a template. To explore their properties, we have prepared three different mechanically-interlocked nanographenes (**1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C**) with macrocycles that show different aromatic sidewalls (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Representative examples of π -conjugated 1D materials including the nitrogenated nanographene rotaxanes described in this work.

Thermal, optoelectronic and electrochemical characterization of the different mechanically-interlocked nanographenes evidence enhanced thermal and photochemical stability, and also, absorption and emission properties that vary with the structure of the macrocycle. In some particular cases, new properties, such as dual-fluorescence and intrarotaxane Förster resonance energy transfer (FRET), have also been observed.

Synthesis

Mechanically-interlocked nanographenes **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C** with different sidewalls were prepared by a clipping strategy

using a Leigh-type reaction (Scheme 1), where the hydrogen bond accepting sp^2 nitrogens of nanographene **1** framework serve as a template for the different tetralactam macrocycles (see also X-ray characterization below). Different sidewalls (benzene, anthracene and benzodithiophene) were selected to study the influence of the macrocycle on the the properties of nanographene **1**. We have selected this type of tetralactam macrocycles because they have been found to form around a large number of templates and recognize several structures,¹⁹ and also to accommodate a variety of organic dyes, sugars, and even inorganic ions.²⁰

The synthesis of the mechanically-interlocked nanographenes required first the synthesis of nanographene **1** and of some of the precursors of the tetralactam macrocycles (Scheme 1a). Nanographene **1** was synthesized by a new synthetic route that required the desymmetrization of pyrene along the K-regions. Even if the backbone of nanographene **1** has been previously reported, it is known to be largely insoluble.²¹ The solubility of the dumbbell component in chlorinated solvents is an unavoidable prerequisite for this type of hydrogen bond assisted ring-forming reactions.²¹ To ensure a high solubility, we incorporated alkoxy chains in the 4,5 positions and *tert*-butyl substituents in the 2,7 positions of the pyrene residue. Tetraone **2** was synthesized in two steps following a procedure described by Harris.²² Then, **2** was reduced with sodium dithionite and alkylated *in situ* with hexyl bromide to obtain tetraether **3** (51%). Two adjacent ethers from one of the K-regions of tetraether **3** were selectively hydrolyzed and oxidized in one single step by addition of 4 equivalents of bromine at 0°C, yielding dione **4** (71%). Nanographene **1** (76%) was obtained by a double cyclcondensation between dione **3** and tetraamine **5**.

The synthesis of mechanically-interlocked nanographenes **1@A** (24%), **1@B** (34%) and **1@C** (18%) was achieved by a slow and simultaneous addition of a solution of 2,6-pyridinedicarbonyl chloride (**9**) and of a solution of the corresponding diamine (either *p*-xylylenediamine **10**, 9,10-bis(aminomethyl)anthracene **11**,²³ or bis(aminomethyl)-2,6-dihexylbenzodithiophene **8**) to nanographene **1** (Scheme 1c). 3,7-Bis(aminomethyl)-2,6-dihexylbenzodithiophene **8** was synthesized in two steps from 2,6-dihexylbenzodithiophene (**6**)²⁴ (Scheme 1b), by introducing first bromomethyl groups in positions 3 and 7 (**7**, 96%) and then by replacing the terminal bromides with amines (**8**, 45%).

Structural Characterization

The structure of the three mechanically-interlocked nanographenes was confirmed by ¹H-NMR, ¹³C-NMR and HRMS (details in the Supporting Information). The formation of the rotaxanes can be easily confirmed by ¹H NMR (Figure 2). For instance, protons A and B in **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C** are shifted upfield in comparison to those of nanographene **1** ($\Delta\delta_A = -0.22, -0.38$ and -0.43 and $\Delta\delta_B = -0.92, -1.42$ and -1.67 , respectively) as the result of the shielding of the macrocycle. Also, the amide protons of the macrocycle appear between 9.5 and 10.5 ppm in CDCl₃, which indicate that they are engaged in hydrogen bonds with the nitrogen atoms of the pyrazine rings in nanographene **1**, which is also confirmed by X-ray characterization below.

The structure of **1** and **1@B** was also confirmed by single-crystal X-ray diffraction (Figure 3). The crystal structure of nanographene **1** shows that the aromatic core is almost flat with the pyrene residues slightly out of plane adopting a sigmoidal structure (Figures 3a-c). The molecules of nanographene **1** in the crystal are slip-stacked at a π -stacking distance of 3.6 Å with a slip angle of 75° (Figures 3b and 3c). The crystal structure of **1@B** evidence that the macrocycle is mechanically-interlocked to the nanographene component and also that the macrocycle is engaged in hydrogen bonds (average distance 2.4 Å) through the amides to one of the pyrazine rings on the nanographene residue (Figures 3d-f). The anthracene rings of the macrocycle are π -stacked with the nanographene component at distance of 3.5 Å. The encapsulated nanographene is slightly twisted by 7°. The molecules of **1@B** in the crystal are π -stacked one on top of the other through the anthracene sidewalls in 1D columnar fashion at a distance of 3.5 Å (Figure 3e and 3f).

Figure 2. Partial ¹H-NMR spectra of a) **1**, b) **1@A**, c) **1@B** and d) **1@C**. Solvent residual peaks are indicated with asterisks.

Figure 3. (a) X-Ray crystal structure of **1**. (b,c) Molecular packing of **1**. (d) X-Ray crystal structure of **1@B**. (e,f) Molecular packing of **1@B** (hexyl chains have been removed for clarity).

Thermal and Photochemical Stability

The thermal stability of nanographenes **1**, **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C** was investigated by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) (Figures S1-S4). The decomposition temperature of the mechanically-interlocked nanographenes (T_d) is higher in all cases when compared to nanographene **1** ($\Delta T_d = 50, 90$ and 90 °C, respectively for **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C**). These differences evidence the thermal stabilizing effect of the macrocycle, which increases with the size of the sidewall (benzodithiophene = anthracene > phenylene).

Table 1. Thermal stability of **1**, **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C**.

	1	1@A	1@B	1@C
T_d (°C) ^a	240	310	350	350
ΔT_d (°C) ^b	–	50	90	90

^a T_d corresponds to onset of the decomposition transition. ^b $\Delta T_d = T_d^{1@X} - T_d^1$.

The photochemical stability of the different nanographenes was also investigated upon exposure to UV radiation (270 nm) in argon saturated chloroform solutions (Figure 4). While a solution of nanographene **1** only retain 46% of the initial absorbance at the lowest energy absorption band after 5 min, solutions of the mechanically-interlocked nanographenes **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C** retained respectively 86%, 71% and 56% the original absorbance, which again evidence the stabilizing effect of the macrocycle (phenylene > anthracene > benzodithiophene).

Figure 4. Photostability of **1**, **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C**.

Electronic Absorption Properties and Energy Levels

Chloroform solutions of **1**, **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C** display different vivid colors; namely pink, blue, blue and purple, respectively (Figure 5 insets). These color differences are quite remarkable since the benzene, anthracene and benzodithiophene dyes on the sidewalls do not absorb light in the visible. The electronic absorption spectra in chloroform show in all cases a broad band in the visible with vibronic features centered in the nanographene component, and also, an overlap of different bands in the UV region (Figure 5). In nanographene **1**, the lowest energy absorption band appears at 571 nm. In the rotaxanes this absorption band is broadened and bathochromically shifted. Different shifts are observed for different macrocycles (41, 42, and 24 nm respectively for **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C**), which evidence how the optoelectronic properties of nanographene **1** can be modulated by the influence of macrocycle. In addition, the absorption in the UV region varies

with the nature of the macrocycle and in the case of **1@A** resembles the absorption of **1**, meanwhile in the case of **1@B** and **1@C** clear differences can be observed.

Figure 5. Absorption and fluorescence (colored trace) of a) **1** ($\lambda_{exc} = 550$ nm), b) **1@A** ($\lambda_{exc} = 550$ nm), c) **1@B** ($\lambda_{exc} = 270$ nm) and d) **1@C** ($\lambda_{exc} = 270$ nm) in chloroform. Rayleigh scattering bands are indicated with asterisks.

Time-dependent DFT calculations (B3LYP-6-311+G(2d,p)/M06-2X-6-31G(d,p)) were carried out to shine light on the nature of the low energy excitations of **1**, **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C**. The calculations show that the lowest energy band corresponds mainly to a HOMO→LUMO transition for **1** and **1@A**, and to a HOMO-2→LUMO transition for **1@B** and **1@C** with a contribution $\geq 97\%$. The fact that these differences do not have an important influence on the electronic absorption spectra can be easily explained by observing the electron-density distribution of the orbitals involved (marked with stars in Figure 6a). In all cases, the LUMO orbital is centered on the nanographene component showing a similar electron-density. Similarly, the HOMO orbitals in **1@A** and the HOMO-2 in **1@B** and **1@C** are also centered on the nanographene component and also show a similar electron-density distribution. In other words, the fact that the absorption

spectra show similar features is because the transitions of **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C** fundamentally come from the encapsulated nanographene, while the differences can be ascribed to the interaction with the sidewalls of the different macrocycles.

The optical energy gaps (E_{GAP}) were estimated from the onset of the absorption spectra (Figure 5) and the electrochemical LUMO levels (or electron affinity) were estimated from onset of the first reduction wave of the cyclic voltammograms (Figure S5), which together provided a complete picture of the energy of the frontier orbitals and how they are affected by the presence and the nature of the interlocked macrocycle. The optical E_{GAP} of rotaxanes **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C** (1.94, 1.94 and 1.97 eV, respectively) are smaller than those observed for nanographene **1** (2.05 eV). The electrochemical LUMOs of the rotaxanes **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C** (-3.75, -3.65 and -3.62 eV, respectively) are destabilized by the presence of the interlocked macrocycle in comparison to nanographene **1** (-3.87 eV). The energy of the HOMO levels of the rotaxanes **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C** (-5.69, -5.59 and -5.59 eV, respectively), estimated by the difference between the electrochemical LUMO and the optical E_{GAP} , are also destabilized by the presence of the interlocked macrocycle in comparison to nanographene **1** (-5.92 eV).

Figure 6. a) Frontier orbitals of **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C**. The orbitals involved in the lowest energy absorption bands are marked by stars. b) Experimental energy levels of **1**, **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C**.

Fluorescence, Dual Fluorescence and FRET

The emission spectra show in all cases a featureless fluorescence band that emerges from the lowest energy absorption band (Figure 5). The fluorescence wavelengths of the rotaxanes are bathochromically shifted for **1@A** and **1@B** (14 and 20 nm respectively) and hypsochromically shifted for **1@C** (-5 nm) with respect to nanographene **1**, which again evidence how the emission of **1** can be non-covalently modulated by the different macrocycles. This trend differs to that observed on electronic absorption and is explained by the smaller bathochromic shift with respect to nanographene **1** and the smaller Stokes shift observed in **1@C** (29 nm, 781 cm^{-1}) in comparison **1@A** (31 nm, 788 cm^{-1}) and **1@B** (37 nm, 931 cm^{-1}). The quantum yields for nanographene-centered fluorescence are 0.25, 0.05, 0.15 and 0.17, respectively for **1**, **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C**.

Remarkably, upon excitation at 270 nm, dual fluorescence can be observed for **1@B** and **1@C** (Figure 5c and 5d). This means that in addition to the nanographene-centered fluorescence described above, an additional fluorescence band from the interlocked macrocycles is also observed. This second band is consistent with the fluorescence of anthracene and benzodithiophene, respectively for **1@B** and **1@C** (Figure S6). The presence of this additional fluorescence band can be explained by the high energy excitation wavelength used (270 nm). At this wavelength both the macrocycle and nanographene components of **1@B** and **1@C** are excited and subsequently deactivate by fluorescence emission, giving rise to the observed dual fluorescence. This implies that the interaction between the two chromophores is not very strong in agreement with the calculations.

In the case of **1@C**, the relative fluorescence intensity of the benzodithiophene-centered band decreases with respect to the intensity of the nanographene-centered band (Figure 7) as we shift the excitation wavelengths into the lowest energy absorption bands of benzodithiophene (300-370 nm, Figure S6 and S7). These changes in the relative fluorescence intensity of **1@C** are the result of FRET. In this particular case, the selective excitation of the benzodithiophene units in the macrocycle is transfer non-radiatively to the nanographene, resulting in the quenching of the fluorescence of the benzodithiophene units and in the enhancement of the fluorescence intensity of the nanographene component.

Figure 7. Fluorescence spectra of **1@C** in chloroform at different wavelengths illustrating FRET. Rayleigh scattering bands are indicated with asterisks.

Conclusions

To conclude, we have described the synthesis of mechanically-interlocked nitrogenated nanographenes **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C** with benzene, anthracene and benzodithiophene sidewalls, respectively. In this family of rotaxanes, nanographene **1** serves as a dumbbell and also as a template. The nitrogen atoms in the nanographene framework assist the clipping reaction of the macrocycle by hydrogen bonding interactions, evidenced by NMR and by single crystal X-ray diffraction. The thermal and photochemical stability of the mechanically-interlocked nanographenes **1@A**, **1@B** and **1@C** is higher in comparison to that of nanographene **1**, which illustrates the stabilizing effect of the macrocycle. In addition, absorption, fluorescence and electrochemical measurements show that the macrocycle can modulate the optoelectronic and redox properties of nanographene **1** and also can introduce new ones. For instance, **1@B** and **1@C** exhibit dual-fluorescence and **1@C** exhibit intrarotaxane FRET from the macrocycle to the encapsulated nanographene. Overall this work makes available method to prepare mechanically-interlocked nitrogenated nanographenes and provides proof-of-concept of the effects that the interlocked macrocycle can have on their properties. We anticipate that this method will generate a broader variety of larger mechanically-interlocked systems that contain fused nitrogenated nanographene residues, such graphene nanoribbons and fused-aromatic networks, and will open the door to new families of synthetic materials that combine the properties of graphene derivatives with the dynamic properties of rotaxanes.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website.

Experimental details of the synthesis, characterization and calculations. Crystallographic data for **1** (2033834) and **1@B** (2033835) are also deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre.

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Author Contributions

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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